

ESD Ideas: Climate tipping is not instantaneous - the duration of an overshoot matters – Supplementary Material

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In this Supplementary Material we detail the methods used to implement the inverse square law theory (Ritchie et al., 2019), advanced to support this ESD Ideas analysis. Specifically, we determine the characteristics of global warming overshoot profiles that avoid tipping for different elements of the Earth system, based on their global warming threshold (i.e. equilibrium warming of activation) and tipping timescale. These two statistics are available for a large number of tipping elements, as
5 provided in a recent assessment (Armstrong McKay et al., 2022). Here, the “overshoot” warming profiles are defined in terms of the peak global warming and the time over 1.5°C.

From dynamical systems theory, we assume that each tipping element can be characterised by a single ordinary differential equation of the form

$$\dot{x} = f(x, q(t)), \tag{1}$$

10 for some external forcing $q(t)$, assumed to be a time-evolving bifurcation parameter with a fold bifurcation at $(x, q) = (x_b, q_b)$. Here, x is the main variable that describes a tipping element and passing a tipping point corresponds to its value “jumping” to a new value. Forcing, q (°C), is the global warming trajectory.

The inverse square law theory (Ritchie et al., 2019) describes peak overshoots, $q_{\text{peak}} - q_b$, (here, units of °C) and tipping threshold exceedance times, t_e , (here, years) that avoid tipping, as given by the condition:

$$15 \quad (q_{\text{peak}} - q_b)t_e^2 < \frac{4}{a_0^2 \kappa}, \tag{2}$$

where the parameters a_0 and κ are properties of system, Eqn. (1), given by:

$$a_0 = \left. \frac{\partial f}{\partial q} \right|_{(x_b, q_b)}, \quad \text{and} \quad \kappa = \left. \frac{1}{2a_0} \frac{\partial^2 f}{\partial x^2} \right|_{(x_b, q_b)}. \tag{3}$$

However, for the purposes of this study, we are interested in the time over, t_{over} (yr), an arbitrary predefined level in external forcing q_{lev} (later assumed to be one of the Paris targets of 1.5°C of global warming). This is different to most previous
20 analysis, which considers the time over an individual tipping element threshold, q_b . To account for this change, instead we use

the formalism introduced in Lux-Gottschalk and Ritchie (2024) that returns the new conditions of:

$$t_{\text{over}}^2 < \frac{4(q_{\text{peak}} - q_{\text{lev}})}{a_0^2 \kappa (q_{\text{peak}} - q_b)^2}. \quad (4)$$

Note that as expected, setting the arbitrary level to be the tipping threshold (i.e. $q_{\text{lev}} = q_b$) reverts Eqn. (4) back to the inverse square law of Eqn. (2).

25 For our analysis we modify a conceptual dynamical model introduced by Wunderling et al. (2021) but assume no coupling between different tipping elements. We introduce a scaling parameter, β (that scales between temperature and the units of the state variable x), and a dimensionless parameter, α , that determines how quickly the stability of the initial stable state decreases as the bifurcation approaches (that is, described by the curvature of the equilibrium branch). For each tipping element, indexed by i , the model is given by:

$$30 \quad \tau_i \frac{dx_i}{dt} = -\frac{4\alpha_i^3}{27\beta_i^2 \Delta T_{\text{crit},i}^2} x_i^3 + \alpha_i x_i + \beta_i \Delta T, \quad (5)$$

where the external forcing is now represented by global warming, $\Delta T(t) = q$, and each tipping element has a critical level of global warming, $\Delta T_{\text{crit},i} = q_b$ and a tipping timescale, τ_i . Alternatively, if we introduce a new parameter $\gamma_i = \beta_i/\alpha_i$ then equation (5) becomes

$$\tau_i \frac{dx_i}{dt} = -\frac{4\alpha_i}{27\gamma_i^2 \Delta T_{\text{crit},i}^2} x_i^3 + \alpha_i x_i + \alpha_i \gamma_i \Delta T, \quad (6)$$

35 and so without loss of generality we can set $\alpha_i = 1$, otherwise this is equivalent to redefining the timescale τ_i .

Using the definitions of Eqn. (3), the parameters a_0 and κ for each tipping element, modelled by equation (6), are given as:

$$a_{0,i} = \frac{\gamma_i}{\tau_i}, \quad \text{and} \quad \kappa_i = \frac{2}{3\gamma_i^2 \Delta T_{\text{crit},i}}. \quad (7)$$

Substituting Eqn. (7) into Eqn. (4) yields the criterion for the time allowed over $1.5^\circ\text{C} = q_{\text{lev}}$, that avoids tipping based on the peak in global warming ($\Delta T_{\text{peak}} = q_{\text{peak}}$, ($^\circ\text{C}$)), and the critical warming threshold, ΔT_{crit} , and tipping timescale, τ , of the

40 tipping element:

$$t_{\text{over},i}^2 < \frac{6\tau_i^2 \Delta T_{\text{crit},i} (\Delta T_{\text{peak}} - 1.5)}{(\Delta T_{\text{peak}} - \Delta T_{\text{crit},i})^2}. \quad (8)$$

The values of $\Delta T_{\text{crit},i}$ and τ_i are adopted directly from Armstrong McKay et al. (2022). Note that the parameter, γ_i , does not feature in Eqn. (8) and so its choice does not impact the overshoot duration.

It is Eqn. (8) that allows us to build Figure 1 in the main paper, to determine whether tipping activation is triggered for each

45 Earth system element, and for different values of t_{over} and ΔT_{peak} . Specifically, the best estimates from the Armstrong McKay et al. (2022) study are used in panel (c), but panels (a) and (b) also make use of the lower and upper estimates to generate an uncertainty range for the number of tipped elements as described in the following section.

Panels (a) and (b) in Figure 1 of the main paper, plot the probability density for the number of tipped elements in colour. An exponentially modified Gaussian distribution, to accommodate skewed distributions, is fitted, using least squares, to each ele-

50 ment's tipping timescale and threshold location. This is performed by fitting the lower, best, and upper estimates to correspond

to the 5, 50, and 95% cumulative probability density levels. Note, for the coral reefs, East Antarctic ice sheet, and the Barents sea ice only one timescale estimate is given and so these are assumed to have no uncertainty. Similarly, the upper estimate for the timescales of the boreal forests are unknown and so the upper estimate takes the value of the best estimate for both dieback and expansion respectively, these modifications are included in Table 1. A random sample is then drawn from each of the 32 distributions to provide the threshold location and tipping timescale for each of the 16 tipping elements. Assuming these threshold and timescale values the inverse square law is used as previously to calculate the number of elements that would tip for each warming scenario. The process is repeated 1,000 times to thus generate the probability density for the number of tipped elements for each scenario.

Table 1. Table of tipping elements used in the study with estimates for their temperature thresholds and tipping timescales. Values taken from Armstrong McKay et al. (2022) with the lower, best, and upper estimates assumed to take the 5%, 50% and 95% cumulative probability density levels respectively.

Tipping Element	Temperature thresholds ($^{\circ}C$)			Tipping timescales (years)		
	5%	50%	95%	5%	50%	95%
Subpolar Gyre (collapse)	1.1	1.8	3.8	5	10	50
Coral Reefs (die-off)	1.0	1.5	2.0	10	10	10
Arctic Winter Sea Ice (collapse)	4.5	6.3	8.7	10	20	100
Barents Sea Ice (loss)	1.5	1.6	1.7	25	25	25
Boreal Permafrost (collapse)	3.0	4.0	6.0	10	50	300
Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (collapse)	1.4	4.0	8.0	15	50	300
Sahel and W. African Monsoon (greening)	2.0	2.8	3.5	10	50	500
Amazon Rainforest (dieback)	2.0	3.5	6.0	50	100	200
Boreal Forest (dieback)	1.4	4.0	5.0	50	100	100
Boreal Forest (expansion)	1.5	4.0	7.2	40	100	100
Boreal Permafrost (thaw)	1.0	1.5	2.3	100	200	300
Mountain Glaciers (loss)	1.5	2.0	3.0	50	200	1k
West Antarctic Ice Sheet (collapse)	1.0	1.5	3.0	500	2k	13k
East Antarctic Subglacial Basins (collapse)	2.0	3.0	6.0	500	2k	10k
Greenland Ice Sheet (collapse)	0.8	1.5	3.0	1k	10k	15k
East Antarctic Ice Sheet (collapse)	5.0	7.5	10.0	10k	10k	10k

60 **References**

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